

CHEMICAL PLATING OF CHOPPED SiC FIBER

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SUMMARY: The activation and chemical plating technology of FeCo alloy coating on the surface of SiC fiber was studied and optimized, a kind of rounded and even coating could be produced according to the optimized technology. The deposition velocity function of the coating was determined. The tensile strength of SiC fiber after activation, plating and heat-treatment were measured, and the results showed that the intrinsic strength of SiC fiber did not decrease during these activation, plating or heat-treatment. The permeability and permittivity (at X band) of CoFe-coated SiC fiber was tested, and the influence of preparation condition on the electromagnetic property of the modified SiC fiber was investigated. The conclusion was that the modified SiC fiber is magnetic ($\mu' > 1$) and its permittivity can be adjusted in a wide range.

KEYWORDS: SiC fiber, chemical plating, permittivity, permeability

INTRODUCTION

As an excellent reinforcement, SiC fiber has interested researchers for many years. On the other hand, SiC fiber is a potential microwave absorbent for structural RAM (radar absorbing material) as long as its permittivity and permeability were well tailored. A usual process is to introduce some metal elements into the raw material chemically or physically. Unfortunately, the content of the additives is restricted by the spinning technology. So the electromagnetic parameters of the product can only be adjusted in rather narrow range. Another way to decrease the resistivity of SiC fiber is to coat it with carbon. The weak point of this method is that carbon-coated SiC fiber is non-magnetic, and complicated equipment is required. To solve these problems, we developed a chemical plating technology to prepare magnetic metal coating (Co and Fe/Co alloy) on the surface of SiC fiber to increase its permeability and permittivity. Although this technology has been developed based on chopped SiC fiber, it is also capable of modifying continuous SiC fiber.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Activation of SiC fiber

SiC fiber can not be chemically plated directly, so it must be activated prior to plating. The key of activation is to deposit some active metal (usually Pd) on the surface to plate. By referring to the activating methods for other non-metallic materials such as ceramic and plastic (these methods have been proved not applicable for SiC fiber), we developed an effective activation technology for plating Co, Fe and FeCo alloy on SiC fiber, which consists of four steps, as shown in Table 1. It has been found that the most important step to ensure

successful plating is coarsening, and the second one is activation. All process were carried at room temperature.

Table 1: Activating technology for SiC fiber

Step	coarsening	sensitization	activation	reduction
Time, min	10-30	5-10	5-10	5-10
reagents	CrO ₃ , HF, H ₂ SO ₄	SnCl ₂ , HCl	PdCl ₂ , HCl	Na ₂ P ₂ O ₄

Chemical plating of SiC fiber: technology and mechanism

The technology (composition of the plating solution, temperature and pH value) of Chemical plating (Co, Fe, or FeCo alloy) on metal substrate has been well studied. Those reported methods could be used for SiC fiber when some adjustment was adopted to ensure the stability of the plating solution, the deposition velocity and the quality of the coating. We obtained the optimized solution composition with FeSO₄ and/or CoSO₄ as main salt, NaBH₄ or NaH₂PO₂ as reducer to obtain different coatings, as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Composition of chemical plating solution for SiC fiber

Coating	Co(P)	Co(B)	FeCo(P)	FeCo(B)
Composition of the solution	CoSO ₄	CoSO ₄	FeSO ₄ , CoSO ₄	FeSO ₄ , CoSO ₄
	NaH ₂ PO ₂	NaBH ₄	NaH ₂ PO ₂	NaBH ₄
	HBO ₃	C ₂ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂	Na ₃ C ₆ H ₅ O ₇	C ₂ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂
	NaKC ₄ H ₄ O ₆	NaKC ₄ H ₄ O ₆	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	NaKC ₄ H ₄ O ₆
Temperature, □	90	90	85	90
pH	9	-	8	8

In order to control the thickness of the coating, the mechanism of Co-P and Co-B deposition has been investigated. The deposition velocity can be described as:

$$v=k \cdot [\text{Co}^{2+}]^a \cdot [\text{RA}]^b \cdot [\text{L1}]^c \cdot [\text{L2}]^d \cdot [\text{H}^+]^e \cdot \exp(-E_d/RT) \quad (1)$$

Where k is the velocity constant, RA represents reducing agent, L1 is complexant and L2 is pH-stabilizing agent. The reactant exponents, a , b , c , d and e , have been determined by experiment (see Table 3). Table 3 showed that the relationship between v and [L1] ([L2]) is parabola-like, whatever the reducer is.

Table 3: Reactant exponents of chemical plating of Co-P and Co-B

	a	b	c	d	e	$-E_d/R$
Co-P	1.01	2.07	-1.74, [L1]>0.67mol/l	-0.92, [L2]<0.59mol/l	-1.25	-6821
			1.56, [L1]<0.67mol/l	0.93, [L2]<0.59mol/l		
Co-B	0.65	0.10	0.44, [L1]<0.22mol/l	2.82, [L2]<0.46mol/l	-0.62	-33300
			-2.67, [L1]>0.22mol/l	-2.48, [L2]>0.46mol/l		

The weight ratio of Fe to Co in the deposited coating can be controlled by altering the ratio of [Fe²⁺] to [Co²⁺] in plating solution[1], as shown in equation 2:

$$\text{Fe/Co}=(k_{\text{Fe}} \cdot [\text{Fe}^{2+}]^a)/(k_{\text{Co}} \cdot [\text{Co}^{2+}]^b) \quad (2)$$

The type of the $\text{Fe/Co}-[\text{Fe}^{2+}]/[\text{Co}^{2+}]$ curve is up to a and b . The curve is linear only when $a=b=1$, as shown in Fig. 1. Fig. 1 showed that higher Fe content can be obtained when using NaBH_4 as reducing agent. This is important to increase μ' and μ'' of the modified SiC fiber.

Fig. 1: The composition of FeCo coating as function of $[\text{Fe}^{2+}]/[\text{Co}^{2+}]$

Strength and electromagnetic property of FeCo coated SiC fiber

The apparent strength of FeCo coated SiC fiber decreased during activation, plating and heat-treatment, which can be explained by two reasons: FeCo coating enlarged the apparent diameter of the fiber but contributed no strength, and more surface defects formed during coarsening (see Fig. 2). Fig. 2 also showed that the residual strength of the modified SiC fiber is high enough to be reinforcement as well as absorbent for structural RAM.

Fig 2: Scheme of the strength of SiC fiber as a function of the apparent diameter

Note: 1. the solid line is the theoretical relationship between the strength of SiC fiber and its apparent diameter; 2. Data point A: SiC fiber, B: after coarsening, C: after reduction, D: after plating Co(P), E1: FeCo(P) coated 'D' fiber, E2: FeCo(B) coated 'D' fiber, F1: heat-treated 'E1' fiber, F2: heat-treated 'E2' fiber.

Electromagnetic property of FeCo coated SiC fiber

The electromagnetic property of the Co and/or Fe coated SiC fiber can be modified by altering the composition of the coating, the sequence of the multi-layered coatings and the heat treatment condition. The permeability and permittivity of the products can be adjusted in rather wide range: ϵ' : 10-100, ϵ'' : 0-100, μ' : 0-2, μ'' : 0-1.5 (8-12GHz).

We found that it is comparatively easy to adjust the permittivity of FeCo coated SiC fiber. For example, ϵ' and ϵ'' will increase when the thickness or the Co content of the coating increases, and they will decrease when heat-treated in Air. But it is much harder to increase the permeability of the modified fiber. One important clue is that aligning different coatings in some special order is effective to increase μ' and μ'' . Fig. 3 is the compare of the permittivity and permeability curves of some modified SiC fibers with single or double layer of FeCo coating. We know from Fig. 3 that the sequence of coatings is very important for the electromagnetic property of the modified SiC fiber.

Fig. 3: The permittivity and permeability curve of some modified SiC fiber

Note: P, B represent two kind of SiC fibers with single-layered coating, and PB, BP are two kind of modified SiC fibers with double-layered coating consist of P and B.

CONCLUSIONS

The activation and chemical plating technology were optimized, which could ensure successful deposition of FeCo coating on the surface of SiC fiber. The relationship between the composition of the FeCo coating and the plating solution was studied. The Fe/Co-[Fe²⁺]/[Co²⁺] curve was linear for FeCo(P) but non-linear for FeCo(B). The decrease of the tensile strength of SiC fiber was mainly due to the increase of its parameter, and the modified SiC fiber was tough enough to be reinforcement for structural RAM. The permittivity of the modified SiC fiber could be adjusted in a wide range, and its permeability could be improved by multi-layer coating.

REFERENCES

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